

FAIRsharing Data Preservation Policy

Version 0.1, 2023-12-01

Aim

To preserve the data currently stored in the FAIRsharing.org database in the event that the FAIRsharing service is no longer able to continue.

Data Formats

FAIRsharing contains bespoke, curated information about Database, Standard and Policy resources, including Collections of these three resources. A record viewed on the FAIRsharing site (e.g. <https://fairsharing.org/1347>) is comprised of information from three sources:

1. Record metadata. These are stored in a JSON format and validated against a combination of three JSON schemas:
 - a. A schema relevant to all FAIRsharing records.
 - b. A schema specific to the record's registry (Database, Standard or Policy).
 - c. A schema specific to the type of record within each registry, e.g. a knowledgebase (Database) or model/format (Standard).
2. Relations: A FAIRsharing record may be linked to other records of the following classes:
 - a. Other FAIRsharing records (the relationship will be labelled).
 - b. Terms from the [DRAO](#) or [SRAO](#) ontologies.
 - c. Other objects, from the following classes:
 - i. User defined tags.
 - ii. Taxonomic (species) terms.
 - iii. Countries.
 - iv. Licences.
 - v. Organisations.
 - vi. Users (who may have created the record, maintain it, or follow it for edit notifications).
3. Edit logs. A JSON formatted log is kept of any changes made to a record.

With the exception of the JSON metadata, the above are closely tied to the implementation of the FAIRsharing database and API, and this software is not guaranteed to be available should there be no further project funding. Therefore, preservation of the data should endeavour to make all of the above available in a format such that it could be ingested into a

new system. This can be done by exporting data in plain text formats such as JSON or CSV text.

Content Coverage

If the FAIRsharing database ceases to exist in its present form, all data mentioned in the previous section will be exported and preserved, with the exception of personal data (usernames and emails) relating to current users of the system.

Implementation

Whilst the project is funded and operating normally, daily exports of the FAIRsharing database are made and copied offsite to tape backup operated by University of Oxford's computing services. These backups can be used to restore a working instance of a FAIRsharing API server, and this capability is tested approximately monthly by restoring data to a test/development server.

The alternative export of data as CSV text and JSON will therefore only be needed if there is a cessation of funding, or other issue which would shut down the project entirely.

Should such an eventuality arise, Rake tasks as part of the FAIRsharing API software would be used to export all data as described under "Data Formats", above. Should the production FAIRsharing server be unavailable for some reason then this operation can be undertaken using a daily backup of the data and the server software installed on a separate system.

Whilst the project is operating, records are curated by hand by both in-house and external volunteer developers. Upon project shutdown, no further editing will be possible until the data have been subsumed into a successor project.

Sustainability Plan

Technical sustainability

FAIRsharing software

The server software is currently closed source and the FAIRsharing client is available as open source software under the GNU Affero General Public License v3.0 licence. Both are maintained on Github.

If necessary, and with preparation, the FAIRsharing server software could also be released as open source software (a licence must first be chosen).

FAIRsharing data

In the event that FAIRsharing is no longer able to maintain content at the primary location, the steps provided in the “Implementation” section will be followed.

Persistent (metadata)data accessibility

FAIRsharing creates DOIs for records on a monthly basis after review by FAIRsharing curators according to our [DOI criteria](#).

Institutional and financial sustainability

FAIRsharing is committed to the continuation of the FAIRsharing database, and to sourcing additional funding on an ongoing basis as required to support all of the operations relating to the running of the database and to implementation of the preservation policy.

In the eventuality that funding for the continuation of the FAIRsharing database should cease and URLs to the content included in the database can no longer be maintained. DOIs registered for FAIRsharing content will be redirected to a ‘reference’ record within the Oxford University Research Archive (ORA). The ORA record will maintain details of the FAIRsharing database as reference for anyone accessing a FAIRsharing DOI, alongside an export of the FAIRsharing data in CSV and JSON. This will be accompanied by appropriate README files detailing onward use and content of the export, alongside links to or further export of the Github repository, containing information on the FAIRsharing client and software.

A ORA record has already been created as reference to the FAIRsharing database and as holding should it be required for the above described purpose – see:

<https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:b9387fff-89c2-4ff8-ad40-06bfaff862df>

Contact

For any questions relating to this policy, please email: contact@fairsharing.org.